

Synthesis of new *N*-lactosylated isodithiobiurets and dithiazolidines (hydrobromide)

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Manuscript received 23 May 2008, revised 10 February 2009, accepted 11 February 2009

Abstract : A series of new 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets and 3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosylimino-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrobromide) have been synthesized by the interaction of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl isothiocyanate with 1-aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides followed by oxidative cyclisation of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret. The identities of these new *N*-lactosides have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, NMR and Mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Lactosyl isothiocyanate, 1-aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides, isodithiobiurets, dithiazolidines.

Introduction

Nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds have been always a major area of interest to a medicinal chemist because of their diverse potential biological activities¹⁻³. The drugs containing 1,2,4-dithiazolidines^{4,5} show a diverse range of physiological activities such as plant growth promoting activity, antituberculosis⁶, antibacterial, anti-cancer and anti-diabetic⁷. The above applications of 1,2,4-dithiazolidines and our interest in the carbohydrate chemistry prompted us to combine them in a single entity. It involves the synthesis of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-g**) and 3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosylimino-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrobromide) (**5a-g**) have been synthesized by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) with 1-aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides⁸ (**3a-g**) and by oxidative cyclization of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-g**) respectively. Required lactosyl isothiocyanate was prepared by the reaction of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl bromide **1** with lead thiocyanate⁹ (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

Several 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-g**) (Scheme 2) were prepared by the condensation of aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides (**3a-g**) and hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-

lactosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) in benzene for 4 h which were then oxidized to 3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosylimino-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrobromide) (**5a-g**) (Scheme 3) with molecular bromine in chloroform medium. The reaction was monitored by TLC. All the products were purified by chloroform-petroleum ether. The structure of the products were confirmed by spectral analysis (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass)¹⁰⁻¹². The specific rotations of the products were also recorded¹³.

Experimental

Specific rotations were measured on Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter at 28 °C in CHCl₃. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI FTIR spectrophotometer (4000–450 cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer operating at 300 MHz. The Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol-SX-102 (FAB) instrument.

*Preparation of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-g**) (Scheme 2) (Table 1) :*

A mixture of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -*D*-lactosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) (0.005 *M*, 5.5 g) and phenyl-*S*-benzyl-isothiocarbamide (**3a-g**) (0.005 *M*, 1.21 g in 30 ml) in benzene was refluxed for 6 h. Then benzene was distilled off and the resulting syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a white

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *p*-tolyl, (g) *m*-tolyl

solid. It was purified by chloroform-petroleum ether to afford **4**.

4a : m.p. 140 °C; yield 70%, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 120^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 3427 (NH), 1729.2 (C=O), 1492.2 (C=N), 1096 (C=S), 854.4 (lactosyl C-H deformation, C=N), 757.4 (C-S), 709.9 cm^{-1} (C-H aromatic); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (ppm) : δ 8.05 (1H, s, NH), 7.12–7.07 (10H, m, Ar-H), 7.14–5.73 (10H, m, lactosyl protons), 5.94 (1H, s, NH), 4.57–4.21 (4H, d, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.91–5.73 (35H, m, 7-COCH₃), 4.55–3.91 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2$); Mass (*m/z*) : 1354 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 1262 ($\text{M}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}$), 1218 ($\text{M}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCS}$), 1052 (HBL^+), 579 (TBG^+), 391 ($\text{TBG}^+-\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$), 335 ($\text{TBG}-\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$), 105 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}^+$) (Found : C, 66.88; H, 4.25; N, 3.08; S, 3.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{76}\text{H}_{63}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$: C, 67.40; H, 4.65; N, 3.10; S, 4.73%).

4c : m.p. 145–148 °C; yield 79%, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 140^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 3448 (NH), 1728.4 (C=O), 1509.4 (C=N), 1070.2 (C=S), 851.8 (lactosyl C-H deformation, C=N), 710.7 cm^{-1} (C-H aromatic); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (ppm) : δ 8.04 (1H, s, NH), 7.09–7.03 (9H, m, Ar-H), 7.14–5.73 (10H, m, lactosyl protons), 5.44 (1H, s, NH), 4.57–4.21 (4H, d, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.91–5.73 (35H, m, 7-COCH₃), 4.45–3.81 (2H, m, CH_2); Mass (*m/z*) : 1388 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 1277 ($\text{M}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}$), 1233 ($\text{M}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCS}$), 1052 (HBL^+), 579 (TBG^+), 391 ($\text{TBG}^+-\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$), 335 ($\text{TBG}-\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$), 105 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}^+$) (Found : C, 64.88; H, 4.15; N, 2.81; S, 3.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{76}\text{H}_{62}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$: C, 66.57; H, 4.46; N, 3.02; S, 4.61%).

Note

Table 1. 1-Aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-g**) (Scheme 2)

Reactant	Product	M p (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%)				[α] _D ²⁸ (c, CHCl ₃)
				Found (Requires)				
				C	H	N	S	
3a (1.21 g)	4a (4.8 g)	140	70	66.88 (67.40)	4.25 (4.65)	3.08 (3.10)	3.98 (4.73)	+120° (c, 0.156)
3b (1.28 g)	4b (4.9 g)	133–135	72	64.98 (66.57)	4.20 (4.46)	2.99 (3.02)	3.90 (4.61)	+135° (c, 0.156)
3c (1.28 g)	4c (5.1 g)	145–148	79	64.88 (66.57)	4.15 (4.46)	2.81 (3.02)	3.98 (4.61)	+140° (c, 0.156)
3d (1.28 g)	4d (5.1 g)	150–152	78	65.56 (66.57)	4.10 (4.46)	2.95 (3.02)	4.08 (4.61)	+90° (c, 0.157)
3e (1.38 g)	4e (5.2 g)	123–125	80	66.52 (67.59)	4.55 (4.75)	3.01 (3.07)	4.11 (4.68)	+88° (c, 0.157)
3f (1.38 g)	4f (5.4 g)	135–138	85	66.75 (67.59)	4.60 (4.75)	2.89 (3.07)	3.97 (4.68)	+130° (c, 0.157)
3g (1.38 g)	4g (5.2 g)	100–102	80	66.78 (67.59)	4.65 (4.75)	2.90 (3.07)	3.67 (4.68)	+110° (c, 0.157)

4f: m.p. 135–138 °C; yield 85%, [α]_D²⁸+130° (c, 0.156 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr): 3467 (NH), 1728.5 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1097.2 (C=S), 834.8 (lactosyl C–H deformation), 710.7 cm⁻¹ (C–H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm): δ 8.02 (1H, s, NH), 7.34–7.07 (9H, m, Ar-H), 7.14–5.73 (10H, m, lactosyl protons), 5.65 (1H, s, NH), 4.57–4.21 (4H, d, -OCH₂), 5.91–5.73 (35H, m, 7-COCH₃), 4.55–3.91 (2H, m, -CH₂), 4.49–2.28 (3H, m, -CH₃); Mass (*m/z*): 1368 (M⁺+1), 1297 (M-C₆H₅NH), 1252 (M-C₆H₅NHCS), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found: C, 66.78; H, 4.65; N, 2.89; S, 3.97. Calcd. for C₇₇H₆₅O₁₇N₃S₂: C, 67.59; H, 4.75; N, 3.07; S, 4.68%).

Preparation of 3-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrobromide) (5a-g) (Scheme 3) (Table 2):

1-Aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (**3g**) (**4a-g**) was made into paste with chloroform (2.5 ml) and to it bromine solution in chloroform (20% bromine in chloroform, v/v) was added dropwise with stirring till the evolution of lachrymatory fumes of benzyl bromide ceased. An orange red sticky mass thus obtained was allowed to stand for 5–6 h. The sticky mass was washed several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and then it was triturated several times with small quantity of ethanol to remove excess bromine to provide **5**.

Table 2. 3-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-5-arylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrobromides) (**5a-g**) (Scheme 3)
Reactant 1-Aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-g**)

Reactant	Product	M p (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%)				[α] _D ²⁸ (c, CHCl ₃)
				Found (Requires)				
				C	H	N	S	
4a (3 g)	5a (2.1 g)	143–145	60	60.78 (61.74)	4.05 (4.10)	3.08 (3.13)	4.58 (4.77)	+60° (c, 0.156)
4b (3 g)	5b (2.5 g)	108–111	70	60.68 (61.99)	3.95 (4.20)	2.99 (3.09)	4.59 (4.72)	+65° (c, 0.153)
4c (3 g)	5c (2.1 g)	110–112	61	61.68 (61.99)	3.75 (4.20)	2.91 (3.09)	4.11 (4.72)	+88° (c, 0.154)
4d (3 g)	5d (1.9 g)	109–113	55	60.58 (61.99)	3.66 (4.20)	2.98 (3.09)	4.27 (4.72)	+110° (c, 0.153)
4e (3 g)	5e (2.0 g)	165–168	59	61.18 (60.21)	3.85 (3.92)	2.96 (3.05)	3.98 (4.65)	+83° (c, 0.156)
4f (3 g)	5f (2.1 g)	133–135	62	59.18 (60.21)	3.65 (3.92)	2.99 (3.05)	4.10 (4.65)	+75° (c, 0.156)
4g (3 g)	5g (2.3 g)	135–137	64	59.78 (60.21)	3.83 (3.92)	2.95 (3.05)	4.18 (4.65)	+90° (c, 0.153)

5a : m.p. 143–145 °C; yield 60%, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 60^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 3414 (NH), 1728.7 (C=O), 1492.4 (C–N), 1270 (C–O), 1068 (C=S), 756.5 (C–S), 853.7 (lactosyl C–H deformation), 479 (S–S), 709.1 cm^{-1} (C–H aromatic); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (ppm) : δ 8.02 (1H, s, NH), 7.34–7.07 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.14–5.73 (10H, m, lactosyl protons), 4.57–4.21 (4H, d, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.91–5.73 (35H, m, 7-COCH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 1341 (M⁺), 1261 (M-HBr), 1158 (M-HBr, C₇H₅NH), 1053 (M-HBr, C₇H₅NH, CHN₂S₂), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 60.78; H, 4.05; N, 3.08; S, 4.58. Calcd. for C₆₉H₅₅O₁₇N₃S₂.HBr : C, 61.74; H, 4.10; N, 3.13; S, 4.77%).

5b : m.p. 143–146 °C; yield 62%, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 75^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 3415.4 (NH), 1726.4 (C=O), 1451.8 (C–N), 1272.4 (C–O), 1068 (C=S), 804 (C–S), 505.9 (S–S), 709.7 cm^{-1} (C–H aromatic); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (ppm) : δ 8.02 (1H, s, NH), 7.14–6.97 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.11–5.74 (10H, m, lactosyl protons), 4.49–4.21 (4H, d, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.91–5.73 (35H, m, 7-COCH₃), 4.39–2.28 (3H, m, $-\text{CH}_3$); Mass (*m/z*) : 1355 (M⁺), 1275 (M-HBr), 1276 (M-HBr protonated), 1175 (M-HBr, C₇H₅NH), 1060 (M-HBr, C₇H₅NH, CHN₂S₂), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 157 (C₁₀H₅O₂), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 60.68; H, 3.95; N, 2.99; S, 4.50. Calcd. for C₇₀H₅₇O₁₇N₃S₂.HBr : C, 61.99; H, 4.20; N, 3.09; S, 4.72%).

5e : m.p. 110–112 °C; yield 61%, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 88^\circ$ (c, 0.156 in CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 3414 (NH), 1727.8 (C=O), 1451.4 (C–N), 1271.1 (C–O), 1068 (C=S), 759.7 (C–S), 478 (S–S), 709.1 cm^{-1} (C–H aromatic); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (ppm) : δ 8.02 (1H, s, NH), 7.34–7.07 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.14–5.73 (10H, m, lactosyl protons), 4.57–4.21 (4H, d, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.91–5.73 (35H, m, 7-COCH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 1375 (M⁺), 1295 (M-HBr), 1296 (M-HBr protonated), 1193 (M-HBr, C₇H₅NH), 1088 (M-HBr, C₇H₅NH, CHN₂S₂),

1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 157 (C₁₀H₅O₂), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 60.18; H, 3.85; N, 2.96; S, 4.11. Calcd. for C₆₉H₅₄O₁₇N₃S₂.Cl.HBr : C, 60.21; H, 3.92; N, 3.05; S, 4.65%).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow for providing the spectra and also to Dr. S. G. Bhadange, Principal, Shri Shivaji College, Akola for providing necessary facilities.

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